

REVIEW ARTICLE ON CONCEPTUAL STUDY OF DHUMPANA

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ABSTRACT

Dhumapana is a classical Ayurvedic procedure involving the inhalation of medicated smoke, described as an integral component of the *Dinacharya*. It is employed not only as a preventive measure but also as a promotive and therapeutic intervention. *Dhumapana* is particularly indicated for the management of *Urdhva Jatrugata Vyadhi* arising due to vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha Doshas*, manifesting as heaviness of the head, headache, rhinitis, ocular and aural pain, cough, and related conditions. The procedure facilitates rapid elimination of vitiated *Kapha* localized in the head region. Hence, *Dhumapana* is commonly advised following the application of collyrium (*Anjana*). The procedure involves inhalation of medicated smoke generated from a *Dhumavarti* prepared using various herbal drugs and administered through a specialized instrument known as *Dhumanetra*. *Dhumapana* acts through both *Shamana* and *Shodhana* mechanisms in the

management of vitiated *Doshas*. This article elaborates on the classical concept, indications, and therapeutic significance of *Dhumapana* as described in Ayurvedic literature.

KEYWORDS: *Dhumapana*, *Urdhva- Jatrugata Vyadhi*, *Dhumavarti*.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda advocates a holistic approach to health, giving equal importance to preventive and curative measures. *Dhumapana* is one such unique therapeutic procedure mentioned under *Dinacharya*, designed to maintain the normal physiology of *Urdhvajatrugata* organs. The procedure involves inhalation of medicated smoke through the mouth or nose, followed by expulsion in a prescribed manner, using a specific instrument (*Dhumyantra*) is known as *Dhumapana*^[1] with the aim of clearing obstructed channels and expelling vitiated *Doshas*.

In classical literature, *Dhumapana*^[2] is indicated in a variety of conditions such as *Pratishyaya*, *Peenasa*, *Kasa*, *Shiroroga*, and *Karnaroga*. Despite its detailed description in ancient texts, *Dhumapana* is often misunderstood due to its superficial similarity to tobacco smoking. Therefore, systematic documentation and scientific interpretation of *Dhumapana* are essential to re-establish its therapeutic value in present-day Ayurvedic practice.

Owing to the increasing prevalence of upper respiratory and ENT disorders, there is a growing need to revisit and scientifically analyze traditional therapeutic measures such as *Dhumapana*. Hence, the present study aims to review the concept of *Dhumapana* as described in classical Ayurvedic literature and to explore its therapeutic relevance in contemporary clinical practice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present review is based on an extensive study of classical Ayurvedic texts including *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, and their commentaries.

The collected data were systematically analyzed and interpreted to present a comprehensive review of *Dhumapana*.

RESULTS

Classification of *Dhumapana*

Acharya Charaka^[3] classified into 3 types.

- (1) *Dainika* (Daily)- *Prayogika*
- (2) *Avasthika*(Conditional)- *Snaihika*
- (3) *Vairechanika*

Acharya Sushruta^[4]: 5 types

- (1) *Prayogika*

- (2) *Snaihika*
- (3) *Vairechanika*
- (4) *Kasaghna*
- (5) *Vamaniya*

Acharya Vagbhata^[5]: 6 types

- 1) *Shamana (Prayogika)*
- (2) *Brimhana (Snaihika)*
- (3) *Sodhana(Vairecanika)*
- (4) *Kasaghna*
- (5) *Vamaniya*
- (6) *Vranadhupana*

Among all the *Dhuma*, only *Prayogika Dhuma^[6]* is indicated for healthy individuals and can be used on the daily basis without any complication.

Preparation of *Dhumavarti^[7]*

Dhumavarti is taken in the length of 12 *Angula*. Soaked in water for a day and night. Wrapped (5 layer) with ribbon of cloth smeared with paste of drugs. Thickness of *Varti* should be of middle portion of thumb. It should be dried in shade not in direct sunlight and should be removed of its reeds. Smear one end of the *Varti* with any suitable fat material like *Ghrita* or oil. Place it in *Dhumanetra*. Then ignite it with fire and use.

Dhumapana Procedure^[8]

Person should sit in straight and attentive position. Initially, bring the respiration to normal state. Keeping the lips and mouth open, slowly suck the smoke from the upper end of the nozzle (*Dhumanetra*). Smoke ingested through mouth and should be exhaled through the mouth itself. If the person inhaled through the nose, inhale slowly through each nostril alternatively after closing the respective alternate nostril. Inhalation should be done thrice(Each time 3 bout should be taken, 1 bout = sucking the smoke and exhale it out). Smoke inhaled through the nose or mouth should be expelled through the mouth because exhaling through the nose may adversely affect the vision.^[9]

Dhumapana Kala^[10]

Prayogika: *Snatva* (After taking bath), *Bhuktva* (After taking food), *Samulikhya* (After vomiting/ emesis, *Kshutva* (After the act of sneezing). *Dantannighrshya* (After brushing teeth), *Navanante* (After *Nasya Karma*), *Anjanante* (After *Anjanakarma*), *Nidrante* (After sleep) These are the 8 *Kala* where there will be dominancy of the *Vata* and *Kaphadosha*, so to eliminate the excessive accumulation of these *Dosha Dhumapana*^[11] should be done.

According to Acharya Sushruta, Prayogika dhumapana should be done

After brushing teeth, after taking bath, After consuming food, After any surgical procedures.

Snaihika: A *Dhumapana* which is done with *Sneha* and a *Dhumapana* which does *Snehana*.^[12] *Snaihika Dhumapana* should be used after passing urine and faeces, sneezing, anger, laugh and coitus.^[13]

Vairechnika: A *Dhumapana* which removes the *Utklishta Dosha*^[14] from nose. It should be done after bath, daysleep (*Diwaswapan*)^[15], Vomiting.

A healthy individual to receive the *Prayogika Dhumapana* should be done 2 times/day.^{[16],[17]}

Snaihika: 1 time in a day till lacrimation begins.^[18]

Vairecanika: 3 to 4 times a day.^[19]

Pramana of the (Prayogika Dhuma Netra)^[20]

36 *Angulas* in length. Breadth of the tip of the nozzle should be *Kolasthipramana*. It should be straight with 3 bulges (3 joints/curve). Should have three chambers/ joints/ curves (*Riju*, *Trikoshafalitam*, *Triparva*). Made up of metals e.g. gold, silver etc.

Benefits of Samayaka Yoga^[21]

Sense of the purity and lightness in *Hridaya*, *Kantha* and all *Indriyas* Lightness in the head and shoulder).^[22] It is very essential to keep all senses disease free and proper functioning for lifelong period. *Dhumpana* plays an important role to achieve this goal.^[23] Elimination of the excessive accumulated *Kaphadosha*. Pacification of the *Vatadosha*.

Features of improper inhalation of Dhumapana or Ayogya Laksana^[24]

Improper cleansing of oral cavity, absence of clarity of voice, Vitiation of the *Kaphadosha* in *Kantha* (Throat), Heaviness of the oral cavity.

Atiyoga Lakshana / Akala Dhuma Laksana

Badhira (Deafness), *Andhya* (Blindness), *Mukatva* (Loss of voice), *Raktapitta* (Epistaxis), *Sirobhrama* (Giddiness)^[25] *Murcha* (Fainting), *Shiroroga* (Head disorder), *Srotaabhighata* (Injury to sense organs).

Benefits of Prayogika Dhumapana

Promotional benefits: Sense of the lightness and pleasure in senses, voice and mind. Enhances the strength of the tooth, hair of head, moustache and beard. Imparts sense of purity and lightness in oral cavity.^[26]

Preventive benefits: *Shirogurava* (Heaviness of head), pain in ear and eye, *Kasa* (Cough), *Hanugraha* (Stiffness of jaws), *Shirasula* (Head ache), *Pinasa* (Rhinitis), *Hikka* (Hiccup), *Manyagraha* (Torticollis), *Ardhavabhedaka* (Headache), *Putigraha* (Pus discharge from nose), *Shvasa* (Dyspnea), *Arochaka* (Loss of taste), *Dantasula* (Tooth ache), *Asyagandha* (Halitosis), *Galasundi* (Uvulitis), *Upajivhika* (Sublingual cyst), *Khalitya* (Hair falls), *Ksavathu* (Sneezing), *Anidra* (Loss of sleep), *Palitya* (Greying of hair), *Adhikatandra* (Stupor), *Mukhasrava* (Excess salivation), *Indralupta* (Alopecia), *Smrtinasa* (Loss of memory), *Urdvajatruroga* (Diseases of head and shoulder), *Svararoga*^[27] (Disorder of voice).

Persons unfit for Dhumapana

Person who have done *Shodhanakarma* (Purificatory procedure) are contraindicated. *Virikta* (After *Virechana* or purgation), *Bastikarma* (After enema), *Rakti* (After raktamokshana or bloodletting).

Disease specific contraindication:- *Visanartha* – poisonous condition, *Shoka* (In grief), *Srama* (Tiredness), *Ama* (Indigestion), *Murcha* (Unconscious), *Pitta* (Pitta dominancy), *Bhrama* (Stupor), *Trishna* (Thirst), *Kricha* (Emaciation), *Madhyapita* (Alcohol consumption), *Dugda-pita*^[28] (Milk consumption).

Contraindication in following activities

Prajagare^[29] (Night wakeful state).

Contraindicated after these foods: *Sneha-pita* (Oleation), *Maksikapita* (Honey intake), *Bhuktvadadyanna* (Curd intake), *Ruksha*^[30] (Dried food).

Conditional contraindication- In *Pittaprakriti*, *Grismakala*, *Pittaprakopakala* (*Sharad Ritu*), *Garbhini*^[31] (pregnancy).

Disease wise contraindication- *Daha* (Burning sensation) *Panduroga* (Anaemia), *Talushosha* (Dryness of palate), *Chardi* (Vomiting), *Siroabhogata* (Head injury), *Udgra* (Belching), *Timira* (Cataract) *Prameha* (Diabetes), *Udara* and *Unmada*, *Uraksata* (Injury to chest), *Durbala* (Weakness), *Urdhvavata*.^[32]

Conditional contraindication- *Bala* (Children), *Vridhdha* (Senile period) in *Alpakapha* (Less *Kapha*).^[33]

Contraindication in food- *Matsya* (Fish), *Yavagupana*.^[34]

Contraindication in activities- *Langhana*^[35] (Fasting / starvation).

DISCUSSION

When the *Dhumapanadravya* is lightened with fire, it releases the smoke, soot and CO₂. Carbon atom in CO₂ has the tendency to stimulate the respiratory center present in brain stem, this may trigger the normal physiological function of respiratory system. Dis-infective action of the *Dhumapana Dravya* like *Haridra*, *Guggulu* and *Vacha* cleanses the respiratory tract, oral cavity and pharynx.^[36]

Dhumpana also indicated in *Vasantritukaal*.^[37] Because the *Kapha Dosha* accumulated in *Hemantaritu* due to *Sheeta Guna* gets liquify in *Vasanritu* by the sunlight. By the use of *Dhumpana* in this season, one should prevent the accumulation of *Dosha* and helps in elimination of *Kaphadosha*. *Dhumpana* is advised as after process of *Nasya*^[38] and *Vamana*^[39] to remove the residual part of accumulated *Dosha* which can cause other diseases. *Shira* (head region) is the place of *Kaphadosha*^[40] so this area is more potent of *Kaphajavyadhi*.

CONCLUSION

* "Prevention is better than cure" so it is better to prevent accumulation of *Dosha* than curing the disease caused by the vitiated *Dosha*. *Dhumapana* is the important method for this. *Dhumapana* is scientific, rational & logical approach in the drug delivery system specially in respiratory system. By *Dhumpana* the drug reaches the desired site of action directly & thus initiate as immediate action. *Dhumpana* act like- Expectorant, protection of mucosa, Liquefy

the increasing secretions etc. In *Dhumpana* volatile oil when administered orally or inhale with steam increase the respiratory secretions by direct stimulation.

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